

Studies on Crown Ethers. Part-I. Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of Benzo-12-crown-4 and Benzo-15-crown-5 Polyethers

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Coccidial infection is a very serious problem for poultry farms. The benzo-15-crown-5 derivatives have been shown to be moderately active agents against the *Coccidia eimeriatenella* in chicken kidney tissue culture¹. This prompted us to prepare crown polyethers with ring size of 12 and 15 atoms.

4'-Formylbenzo-12-crown-4 (**2a**) has been prepared via alkylation of protocatechualdehyde in presence of sodium hydroxide using 1,8-dichloro-3,6-dioxaoctane as the alkylating agent. 4'-Formylbenzo-15-crown-5 (**2b**) is prepared from protocatechualdehyde as reported in the literature¹. A few derivatives (**3a-d**) of **2a-b** have also been prepared.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Ir and ¹H nmr and mass spectra were determined on Shimadzu DR-1 435, Varian CFT-20 and VG-7070G instruments. Elemental analyses were within ± 0.4 to 1% of the theoretical values.

4'-Formylbenzo-15-crown-5 (**2b**) : Compound **2b** was prepared as reported in the literature¹, (28%), m.p. 71-72° (lit. 70-72°).

4'-Formylbenzo-12-crown-4 (**2a**) : A mixture of 3,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde (4.1 g, 30 mmol) and sodium hydroxide (2.5 g, 60 mmol) taken in water (2 ml) and n-butanol (110 ml), was refluxed under nitrogen. 1,8-Dichloro-3,6-dioxaoctane² (5.61 g, 30 mmol) in n-butanol (50 ml) was added to it with stirring during 30 min, and refluxed under nitrogen atmosphere for 27 h. The cooled mixture was then acidified with HCl and filtered. The filtrate was evaporated to dryness and the residue extracted with a mixture of toluene and benzene (9 : 1) at 80-90° for about 30 min. The extract was evaporated to yield a viscous oil which was purified through column chromatography over alumina (neutral).

Evaporation of CHCl₃ and methanol (9 : 1) eluates afforded a viscous oil which was kept for 2 days. On trituration with diethyl ether a white fibrous product was obtained which on crystallisation from ethanol gave the desired product 4'-formylbenzo-12-crown-4 (**2a**; 11%), m.p. 127-29° (Found : C, 61.4; H, 6.18. C₁₃H₁₆O₅ requires : C, 61.9; H, 6.34; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 100, 2 950, 2 850, 1 690, 1 175, 1 250, 1 150; ¹H nmr δ (CDCl₃) 9.45 (1H, s, CHO), 6.60-7.20 (3H, m, ArH), 3.62 (4H, t, O-CH₂CH₂-O), 3.72, 4.02 (8H, t, methylene); m/z (%) 252 (M⁺), 251 (9), 231 (11), 207 (41), 193 (20), 181 (25), 154 (20), 118 (18), 105 (19), 91 (11), 77 (12), 67 (10), 57 (100); ¹³C nmr δ 68.97, 68.75, 68.59, 69.4, 70.38, 71.5, 111.3, 112.1, 126.8, 130.3, 149.2, 154.3, 190.8.

A mixture of 4'-formylbenzo-12-crown-4 (2.52g, 0.01 mol) and 1-hydrazinophthalazine³ (1.6 g,

0.01 mol) in methanol (15 ml) was refluxed in a waterbath for 3 h. The excess of solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and the product obtained was crystallised from ethanol to get the hydrazone derivative (**3c**; 88%), m.p. 225° (Found : C, 63.55; H, 5.18; N, 14.02. C₂₁H₂₂N₄O₄ requires : C, 63.95; H, 5.85; N, 14.21%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 400, 3 050, 2 930, 2 880, 1 615, 1 270, 1 130, 1 050, 1 585, 1 480, 1 380, 1 560, 750 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ (CDCl₃) 9.2 (1H, s, NH), 8.94 (1H, s, N = CH), 6.75–7.31 (8H, complex m, ArH), 3.59, 3.75, 3.89 (12H, overlapping t, methylene); *m/z* (%) 368 (10), 385 (25), 341 (12), 219 (10), 207 (22), 193 (15), 181 (18), 168 (13), 118 (12), 101 (13), 91 (11), 83 (14), 77 (10), 69 (25), 57 (100); ¹³C nmr δ 68.5, 70.3, 111.1, 122.9, 123.0, 123.5, 123.9, 126.1, 127.9, 128.1, 131.3, 147.6, 148.4, 153.0, 163.1. Similarly, 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative (**3a**) was prepared from **2a**.

In the same way, the hydrazones **3b** and **3d** were prepared from 4'-formylbenzo-15-crown-5 with 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine and 1-hydrazinophthalazine respectively : **3b** (65%), m.p. 245° (Found : N, 11.32. Requires : N, 11.76%); **3d** (69%), m.p. 105–07° (Found : N, 11.83. Requires : N, 12.78%).

Antimicrobial activity : All the six crown-polyethers were screened for their antimicrobial

activity using cup-plate method⁴, at a concentration of 50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ using the gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus magaterium* and the gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas fluorescens*. The antifungal testing was carried out against *Aspergillus flavus* and *Candida albicans*. The activity was determined by measuring the zone of inhibition in mm and compared with the known antibiotics : ampicillin, zone of inhibition of 20–22 mm; cephalixin, 19–21 mm; chloramphenicol, 18–25 mm; norfloxacin, 20–33 mm against various strains of bacteria and fungi using 100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentration. Among the compound tested 4'-(2'',4''-dinitrophenylhydrazino)formalbenzo-15-crown-5 showed fairly good antimicrobial activity (14–25 mm), while 4'-(phthalazin-1''-ylhydrazine)formalbenzo-12-crown-4 was moderately active against different strains of bacteria and fungi (15–25 mm).

References

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